

An Empirical Study of Internet Marketing Based on Flipkart

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Aishwariya, G., and M. Abisha. "An Empirical Study of Internet Marketing Based on Flipkart." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 131–35.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412536>

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Abstract

This paper is purely based on the internet marketing relating to their usage and types etc..in which the word internet means needed information, communication and any other sources which are done with the help of the sources called net and which in turn termed as internet.

With the rapid growth in the marketing industry in India, marketing through internet are also increasing very fast and internet have started using innovative methods as compared to last time. As apart of the study, a questionnaire – based survey was conducted in 2019 with 100 respondents “to know their perception towards internet marketing and to evaluate the factors influence the higher level of internet marketing to go higher and higher”.

Although customers cannot be 100% secure against unknown threats, during the purchase/sale of any product with the help of internet marketing. Some of the other improving and promising steps to make the customers are: duplication, compensation of the product offered by customer, misleading of colour display etc..

Keywords: internet marketing, net, communications

Introduction

History of Internet Marketing

The word “Internet Marketing” introduced in the year of 1990s. But it took some years for the marketers and experts to be aware of the uses of digital marketing. The time of invention of internet marketing has not been widely spread due to the less internet deployment. The first e-commerce transaction which is done through the internet was made in the year 1994. Later, Yahoo was launched this year within one year it hit more than the target of 1 million e-commerce transactions. In the year 1997, the first social media site Sixdegrees.com was launched. The golden year (1998) of digital marketing is by launching Google. The year of social media is 2012 where many companies increased their social media budget upto 64%, and they realized these sites which will help them to explore their businesses globally and for the promotion of their products and brands on various social media channels. The word “internet marketing” is also known as “online marketing”, “digital marketing”, “e-marketing”, “web marketing”. To conclude with the Internet marketing is not an easy

task as it is growing exponentially everyday. As the customers are large in number and they are becoming smarter and as their demand increases day to day, companies are trying to come up with new strategies of ideas in the internet marketing.

Role of Internet Marketing Modern Marketing

In earlier days, most businesses are limited and people who reside in the same vicinity of that location will know about those businesses. Nowadays the current scenario has entirely changed, an organization is visible to millions of people at once through this internet marketing. Hence, it increases the visibility of many businesses around the world. The important vital part of this internet marketing is that it does many researches about the taste and preferences, habits, demographics of consumers based on these research surveys the marketers are able to satisfy the target audience i.e., their end consumers. The relationship between business to business (B2B) and business to companies (B2C) are made easily possible by way of world wide reach of the internet. Through these websites, consumers are able to gather more information about the various brands and products.

Advantages of Internet Marketing

Many organizations prefers internet marketing as a tool as it is far cheaper when compared to traditional form of offline marketing to promote their business venture and to make more sales and profits. In addition to this, it is time saving for both the consumer and marketers to find variety of brands and to sell products by sitting at one location. The major advantage of this internet marketing is that it can be able to capture the global consumer (unlike the traditional marketing is restricted within the selected locality). To clarify the consumer with the advertisement of a product is very easy to access as well as it can be accessed from a single location. The Internet Marketing is considered to be an important aspect as it covers the overall communications between consumers and marketers.

Disadvantages of Internet Marketing

When we say the word internet marketing, from the viewpoint of the businessmen it is not so easy to do as it does not happen at a free of cost. It incurs some expenses like cost of hardware and software, website designing, maintenance of the site and their serves, product distribution cost, etc...all of these factors will be taken into consideration while making internet marketing budgets and strategies. These marketing techniques will take some time to create trust among the minds of customers. Hence, to get an instant trust from the customer is a major drawback. A great deal of Skill and knowledge is required for the success of this internet marketing.

Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the awareness of Internet Marketing among customer.
2. To estimate the popular media app Flip kart.
3. To find the various types of Internet Marketing.
4. To order the preferences of customer towards the Internet Marketing.
5. To understand the need of Internet marketing.

Limitations of the Study

1. The sample of consumer was not enough to generalize the findings of the study.
2. The main source of data for the study was primary data with the help of self-administrated questionnaire.

3. Hence the chance of unbiased information is less.
4. People were hesitant to disclose the true facts.
5. The duration of the study is limited to 1 month.

History of Flipkart

The Flip kart is e-commerce based company. It is founded in the year of 2007 in Bengaluru, India. Flip kart has crossed the successful journey of 12 years. Sachin Bansal Binny Bansal is the founder and kalyankrishnamurthy is the CEO of flip kart. no.of employees in flip kart is 30000 this is as per 2016 survey. As per financial year ending 31st march 2018, the flip kart has reached the turnover of \$3.8 billion (Rs.26925 crore). Recently Walmart, a US-based giant retailer has acquired 77% of shares of flip kart on the date of May 9 2018 and the company’s founder holds the balance 23 %.

Its Business Acquisitions and Plans

The Flip kart acquired Myntra whose is online fashion retailer on May 2014 for Rs.20 billion (US\$290 million). It has been a partner of Motorola, an exclusive India retailer of Moto G Smartphone. Subsequently, in July 2014 it partnered with another smartphones launcher Xiaomi. In March 2015, it gave access to its websites on mobile devices and it acquired the market by providing the facility to users to download the site’s mobile app instead. In 2016, it acquired Jabong an online fashion retailer as well as the UPI mobile payments startup PhonePe. Flip kart overtook Amazon India by holding 51% share of all Indian smartphone shipments in 2017.

Origin of Flipkart

India’s first biggest e-commerce startups to achieve such a billion dollar valuation today are made possible by Flip kart. Its success story starts with the two friends SachinBansal andBinnyBansal who worked in Amazon. They both were techies and had a thought to build something new which they won’t want to deal with the marketing and sales. These thoughts made them build a search engine for e-commerce. Finally, they left their job at Amazon to give a shape for their thoughts and that was the genesis of Flip kart. It is not only an e-commerce site for purchase and sales of products of various brands but it also has its own products i.e., in-house products. Flip kart launched its own set of mobile phones, tablets etc.,and a wide range of personal health care products was launched under the name of a brand called “citron”.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire was framed according to the objectives of the study with 13 questions, which is enclosed at the end of the project.

Analytical Tool

Table I
Monthly Income of Respondents

X- number of respondents for monthly income	
Particulars	Percentage
Rs.10000-20000	57
Rs.20000-30000	23
Rs.30000-40000	13
Rs.40000-50000	3
Rs.50000 and above	4

Table I shows that the majority of respondents nearly 57 % falls under the monthly income of 10000-20000 .

Table II
Criteria for Opting Flip Kart

Y- number of respondents opting Flip kart for buying	
Particulars	Percentage
All the above	42
Offers and discounts	24
Time saving	17
Availability of various brands	9
Cost convenient	8

Table II shows that the majority of the respondents nearly 24% opt flip kart because of their offers and discounts.

Karl Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation

x	y	X=x-X-	y=y-Y-	x.y	X ²	Y ²
57	42	37	17	629	1369	289
23	24	3	4.2	12.6	9	17.64
13	17	-7	-2.8	19.6	49	7.84
3	9	-17	-11.9	202.3	289	141.61
4	8	-16	-11.9	190.4	256	141.61
				1053.9	1972	597.7

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= \Sigma X/NY = \Sigma Y/N \\
 &= 100/5 \qquad = 100/5 \\
 &= 20 \qquad = 20
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \Sigma x y / \sqrt{\Sigma x^2 \cdot \Sigma y^2} \\
 &= 1054/1086 \\
 &= 0.97053407
 \end{aligned}$$

Result

There is a positive relationship between the monthly income and the criteria for opting the products in flip kart.

Table III
Occupation of Respondents

X- number of respondents based on their occupation	
Particulars	Percentage
Engineering studies	40
Commerce studies	34
School studies	14
Self employed	10
Others	2

Table III shows that the majority of the respondents nearly 40% are engineering graduates

Table IV
Comfortable Zones of Replacment of Products in Flip Kart

Y-number of respondents comfortable zone of replacing the products in flip kart	
Particulars	Percentage
Agree	56
Neutral	21
Strongly agree	17
Disagree	5
Strongly disagree	1

Table IV shows that the majority of respondents are agreeing with the comfortable zone of replacing the products.

x	y	X=x-X	Y=y-Y	x.y	X ²	Y ²
40	56	20	36	720	400	1296
34	21	14	1	14	196	1
14	17	-6	-3	18	36	9
10	5	-10	-15	150	100	225
2	1	-18	-19	342	324	361
				1244	1056	1892

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= \frac{\sum X}{N} = \frac{\sum Y}{N} \\
 &= \frac{100}{5} = \frac{100}{5} \\
 &= 20 = 20 \\
 r &= \frac{\sum x y}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \cdot \sum y^2}} \\
 &= 0.8801
 \end{aligned}$$

Result

There is a positive relationship between the qualification and comfort ability of replacing the products in flip kart.

Conclusion

This study has helped us to know the level of purchase of the products through flip kart in online marketing. Where in there is also some drawbacks in flip kart where that can be made a improvement to make it more effective and usefulness for the customer and other who make purchase. We also found difficulty in collecting the data since only 57% out of 100% were member in the flip kart and wherein others only make payment and are not member of the flip kart and make only purchase. They should also be known about the membership provided by the flip kart by being so they will get more discounts and offers while making purchase of any products and also may know the notification of any products that they are in need of.